

What do strawberry roots smell like, that *Melolontha melolontha* larvae like them so much? – on the trail of strawberry volatilome

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Abstract: Nowadays, it is becoming more and more evident that soil-dwelling insect herbivores can use volatile organic compounds present in the vicinity of plant roots as cues for host localization and foraging. Our research aims at understanding how this relationship functions for the system composed by strawberry (*Fragaria x ananassa* Duchesne) and European cockchafer (*Melolontha melolontha* Linnaeus.) larvae. Our observations suggest that *M. melolontha* larvae do not show specific food preferences between different strawberry developmental stages. Moreover, we found a set of VOCs (Volatile Organic Compounds) common of each tested strawberry stage, which could mediate the host plant localization process. Results of these studies could be used for the development of novel sustainable plant protection strategies.

Key words: tri-trophic interactions, volatile organic compounds, soil-dwelling insects, herbivory

Introduction

Plants as permanently attached to the ground, had to develop defence mechanisms and communication systems, which could compensate the movement inability. These adaptations may be comprised by emitting a range of chemical compounds, including VOCs. The profile of emitted volatile compounds, including VOCs and essential oils, is called plant volatilome (Maffei et al., 2011). Nowadays, it is becoming more and more evident that soil-dwelling insect herbivores can use VOCs present in the vicinity of plant roots as cues for host localization and foraging. Our research aims at understanding how this relationship functions for the system composed by strawberry (*Fragaria x ananassa* Duchesne) and European cockchafer (*Melolontha melolontha* L.) larvae.

Materials and methods

Two types of experiments were carried out as part of this research. The first one involves identifying VOCs emitted by strawberry roots during greenhouse experiments. Plants are grown in three different substrates: vermiculite, soil from an organic strawberry plantation or soil from an organic strawberry plantation mixed with peat. The VOC profile emitted by plants at different stages of development (pre-flowering plants, flowering plants or fruiting plants) as

well as plants subjected to abiotic (nutrient deficiency) or biotic (*M. melolontha* feeding) stress is studied. VOCs emitted by the plant are adsorbed using the SBSE (Stir Bar Sorptive Extraction) technique directly on polydimethylsiloxane twisters placed in the immediate vicinity of the strawberry roots and then analysed by GC-MC (Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectrometry). The second type of experiments aims to determine the moving behaviour of *M. melolontha* larvae towards strawberry grown in different substrates, being at different stages of development or under stress conditions (analogous to the conditions of the VOC profile study). These tests are carried out in a specially constructed chamber – Soil-Insect toolbox (Furmanczyk et al., 2021). This is a type of container made of transparent plexiglas that allows the growth of strawberry plants as well as tracking and recording the position of the *M. melolontha* larvae in the soil.

Results and discussion

The statistically highest number of identified VOCs was found in vermiculite compared to the other substrates. A higher number of VOCs were recorded in non-sterile substrates compared to sterile substrates, confirming the involvement of microorganisms in VOC production (Sillo et al., 2024). Analysis of the VOCs emitted by strawberry roots at different developmental stages, irrespective of the growth substrate used, made it possible to distinguish a group of compounds common to each stage and specific to plants before flowering or during flowering and fruiting (tetracosane, decanal, nonanal, pentadecanal, acetphenone). *M. melolontha* larvae showed minimally higher motility in vermiculite compared to the other substrates tested. When the food preference of *M. melolontha* larvae was observed, no statistical differences were observed for the different developmental stages of strawberry. These observations therefore suggest the involvement of commonly identified VOCs in the process of host plant localisation and foraging by *M. melolontha* larvae. Experimental verification of this hypothesis will provide a better understanding of underground plant-environment interactions, which may contribute to evolving the direction of plant protection strategies towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly solutions.

Acknowledgements

The research is carried out and funded by the National Science Centre, Poland within the framework of the research project No. 2021/43/D/NZ9/02323 entitled “Volatilome emitted by strawberry roots as a factor influencing the feeding behaviour of *Melolontha melolontha* larvae”.

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